

POWERING PROGRESS: EXPLORING ELECTRIFICATION AND ENERGY DEMAND IN INDIA

Ms. Kesia Varghese

Asst. Professor, Mob- 8237364087

Ms. Vaishali N Kurhekar

Asst. Professor, Mob- 9892334503

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Abstract

Electrification at the regional, state, or national level acts as an indicator of economic activity and growth. To capture the spread of electricity Night Time Light (NTL) or Night Time Luminosity data, via satellite imagery can be used. While increasing luminosity reflects progress on the supply side—indicating India's movement toward complete electrification—it is also important to examine whether this access to electricity is equitable, reliable, and free from frequent disruptions. The paper here is an attempt in this direction where the growing need of India in terms of consumption of electricity along with the scope to bridge the gap between the supply and the demand side will be explored.

Key Words: *Night Time Light, Luminosity, electrification, supply-demand gap.*

Introduction:

Electricity is one of the macro indicators of growth, development and overall welfare of a country. In India, the push towards universal electrification has gained significant momentum over the last two decades. NTL – Night time luminosity becomes a proxy for the spatial and temporal expansion of electricity access. ***According to the Decadal Change of Night Time Light (NTL) over India from Space (2012 – 2021) overall at National level, normalized NTL radiance (Cumulative NTL radiance / Geographic Area) is increased by 43% in the year 2021 w.r.t 2012.*** The report states that there is a significant increase observed in Bihar, Manipur, Ladakh and Kerala. Good increase observed in Arunachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Gujarat. Moderate increase observed in Lakshadweep, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Jharkhand, Haryana, Punjab, West Bengal, Uttaranchal, Karnataka, Odisha, Telangana,

Andhra Pradesh, Nagaland, Chandigarh, Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan, Tripura, Goa, Chhattisgarh, Assam, Andaman and Nicobar, Meghalaya, Jammu & Kashmir. In most of the States, a fall in NTL cumulative radiance observed in the year 2020, and this could be the impact of COVID-19 Pandemic. Again, in most of the States there is a rise observed in the year 2021 for NTL cumulative radiance.

Literature Review:

Dagmawe Tenaw (2025) mentions that despite ambitious electrification programs, a substantial gap remains between the availability of grid infrastructure and actual connections to the grid in the country. To understand the gap it is necessary to estimate the economic growth. Laveesh Bhandari and Koel Roychowdhury (2011) investigates the association between night lights and GDP estimates for India at the district level. It can predict GDP at the district level for developing countries such as India. Hence it is necessary to understand the interaction between population, night lights and economic activity be better understood. Also GDP estimates may adequately capture growth rates. The availability of radiance calibrated night-time imagery for more recent years should help; but if not available, the analysis of historical stable lights that are already in the public domain should reveal greater insights. Henderson, Storeygard, and Weil (2012) were among the first to systematically use night lights data to estimate economic growth. They demonstrated that night lights data can serve as a reliable proxy for GDP, particularly in countries with poor data quality. Their methodology has since been adopted and refined by numerous researchers. (Tejaswini Tabhane,2024) J. Vernon Henderson, Adam Storeygard, David N. Weil (2011) have explored the usefulness of these night lights data to economists studying issues related to economic growth and the national or local level. In particular, they checked the extent to which lights data can augment or entirely replace data on Gross Domestic Product.

In 2015 and 2018, the Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW) conducted two rounds of energy access surveys (Access to Clean Cooking energy and Electricity— Survey of States [ACCESS]) in rural households across six of India's energy-poor states— Bihar, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Uttar Pradesh, and West Bengal.

As per IRES-The India Residential Energy Survey (IRES) 2020, nearly 97 per cent of Indian households are electrified. India has made a commendable effort on household electrification, as 96.7 per cent of Indian households are now connected to the grid, with another 0.33 per cent relying on off-grid electricity sources. However, 2.4 per cent of Indian households still remain unelectrified. Most of the unelectrified households are concentrated in the **rural areas** of **Uttar**

Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Haryana, and Bihar. An average Indian household receives 20.6 hours of power supply from the grid. The average daily supply in urban areas (22 hours) is longer by a couple of hours than in rural areas (20 hours). Delhi, Kerala, and Gujarat are the top states, maintaining slightly over 23 hours of average supply in both urban and rural areas. In contrast, households in Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand, Haryana, Assam, and Bihar face the longest power outages, with rural households in these states facing six or more hours of daily outages. **Power outage duration and frequency are higher in Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand, Assam, Bihar, and Haryana.** A third of households also faced at least one of the three supply quality issues—long blackouts, low voltages, or appliance damage due to voltage fluctuations—during the month preceding the survey. Only six per cent households reportedly registered a complaint in the past six months, indicating high consumer inertia or low awareness about their rights as electricity consumers. The report reveals that equitable access, reliability of supply, and freedom from frequent power disruptions remain persistent challenges.

Objectives:

1. To trace the extent of electrification in India.
2. To check for the status of outages for states with special focus on Bihar.
3. To draw attention to the future gap between the demand and supply of electricity.

1. To trace the extent of electrification in India.

The Ministry of Power in the Lok Sabha, on electricity cut or power outage provided answers on 03.02.2022 as per the following:

Table 1: State wise Average hours of power outage

State-wise Average hours of Power Outage in a year for last three years and current year till October 2021 (HH.hh) as available on NPP										
As on 28.01.2022										
Sl. No.	State Name	2018-19		2019-20		2020-21		2021-22 (up-to Oct 21)		0
		RURAL	URBAN	RURAL	URBAN	RURAL	URBAN	RURAL	URBAN	
1	Andhra Pradesh	687.42	12.17	134.20	30.50	121.67	36.50	76.37	23.32	99.69
2	Arunachal Pradesh#	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	462.33	0.00	154.23	154.23
3	Assam#\$	0.00	97.33	0.00	73.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	66.32	66.32
4	Bihar	1015.92	0.00	786.90	317.20	772.58	225.08	779.65	94.02	873.67

5	Chhattisgarh	0.00	85.17	0.00	6.10	0.00	6.08	539.40	50.45	589.85
6	Delhi*							0.00	1.27	1.27
7	Goa#\$	0.00	0.00	0.00	457.50	0.00	97.33	0.00	53.39	53.39
8	Gujarat	79.08	18.25	323.30	18.30	97.33	18.25	46.63	12.39	59.02
9	Haryana	1599.92	261.58	1744.60	268.40	1478.25	219.00	1014.37	84.04	1098.41
10	Himachal Pradesh	2986.92	0.00	3056.10	54.90	2980.83	54.75	2562.55	19.90	2582.45
11	Jammu and Kashmir	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	736.08	0.00	257.64	257.64
12	Jharkhand \$	0.00	0.00	0.00	164.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0
13	Karnataka	2323.83	24.33	2482.70	61.00	1758.08	54.75	1082.40	26.64	1109.04
14	Kerala \$	1015.92	0.00	744.20	6.10	1095.00	30.42	670.12	17.23	687.35
15	Madhya Pradesh	243.33	109.50	353.80	54.90	492.75	24.33	228.20	23.50	251.7
16	Maharashtra	0.00	18.25	1299.30	12.20	1107.17	6.08	277.15	4.16	281.31
17	Meghalaya	0.00	18.25	0.00	6.10	0.00	24.33	0.00	18.65	18.65
18	Manipur#\$							0.00	74.91	74.91
19	Mizoram #	0.00	97.33	0.00	122.00	0.00	73.00	0.00	28.09	28.09
20	Nagaland #	0.00	0.00	0.00	183.00	0.00	462.33	0.00	88.81	88.81
21	Odisha \$	1411.33	0.00	1457.90	128.10	997.67	54.75	29.38	58.96	88.34
22	Puduchery \$	693.50	0.00	1299.30	0.00	310.25	0.00	564.45	0.00	564.45
23	Punjab \$	267.67	79.08	305.00	103.70	511.00	85.17	302.40	79.26	381.66
24	Rajasthan	985.50	30.42	988.20	42.70	961.17	6.08	468.12	23.53	491.65
25	Tamil Nadu \$	1180.17	0.00	1110.20	12.20	906.42	0.00	226.77	0.00	226.77
26	Telangana	711.75	0.00	652.70	30.50	675.25	30.42	469.50	16.65	486.15
27	Tripura#\$	1575.58	0.00	1628.70	0.00	1624.25	6.08	223.33	18.98	242.31
28	Uttar Pradesh \$	1788.50	310.25	2549.80	158.60	2761.83	91.25	1749.57	92.00	1841.57
29	Uttarakhand	949.00	194.67	854.00	219.60	742.17	127.75	562.83	98.77	661.6
30	West Bengal \$	2123.08	12.17	341.60	12.20	340.67	6.08	47.30	45.80	93.1

Note 1 Outage Data as submitted by States on NPP. Outage Duration includes both planned and unplanned outage durations.

Note 2 # Only Urban data is Available.

Note 3 \$ States have not submitted data till October 2021 in FY 2021-22.

Note 4 States/UTs not present in the list are not mapped on NPP.
 Note 5* Delhi has been onboarded on NPP in April 2021. So data for previous FYs is not available on NPP .

Source: Government of India ministry of power lok sabha unstarred question no.235 answered on 03.02.2022 electricity cut or power outage

Fig. No:1 Comparative study of the annual outage in rural and urban areas for 2021-22
 According to the above data the top five states with highest total outage are Himachal Pradesh — **2582.45** hours Uttar Pradesh — **1841.57** hours Karnataka — **1109.04** hours Haryana — **1098.41** hours Bihar — **873.67** hours. And the bottom five states with lowest total outages are Goa — **53.39** hours Mizoram — **28.09** hours Meghalaya — **18.65** hours Delhi — **1.27** hours and Jharkhand — **0.00** hours.

While referring to the above report its evident that for a state like Jharkhand **which have not submitted data till October 2021 in FY 2021-22 to reach a conclusion is difficult especially with regards to continuity in supply of electricity.**

Fig.2- Change in the total average outage from 2021-22 vs 2018-19

From the given table above we can conclude that top 05 states that greatest improvement in terms of reduction in outages are **West Bengal (-2042 hrs.), Tripura (-1333 hrs), Odisha (-1323 hrs) Karnataka (-1239 hrs) Tamil Nadu (-953 hrs).** And Top 5 states where outages worsened (increase in hours) are Nagaland (+89 hrs), Arunachal Pradesh (+154 hrs) Jammu & Kashmir (+258 hrs) Maharashtra (+263 hrs) Chhattisgarh (+505 hrs).

Table 2: Urban-rural disparity-2021-22

Based on the data for average hours of power outage in a year during 2021-22, the states/UTs with the highest **urban-rural disparity** (meaning the largest difference between Rural outage and Urban outage) are:

Sl. No.	State Name	Rural Outage (HH.hh)	Urban Outage (HH.hh)	Disparity (Rural - Urban)
10	Himachal Pradesh	2562.55	19.90	2542.65
28	Uttar Pradesh	1749.57	92.00	1657.57
27	Tripura	1749.57	18.98	1730.59
14	Karnataka	1082.40	26.64	1055.76
9	Haryana	1014.37	84.04	930.33
4	Bihar	779.65	94.02	685.63

From the above given table it is compelling to note that:

1. Himachal Pradesh has the most significant disparity, with a Rural outage of 2562.55 hours and a minimal Urban outage of 19.90 hours, resulting in a difference of 2542.65 hours.
2. Tripura and Uttar Pradesh also show a major gap. While Tripura has a large rural-urban difference of 1730.59 hours, the rural outage in Uttar Pradesh is paired with a slightly higher urban outage, leading to a disparity of 1657.57 hours.

3. In all these states, the Rural areas consistently experience significantly longer power outages compared to their Urban counterparts.

Fig. 3: Electricity consumption per capita in different states of India

From **Fig.3**: Bihar’s case is unique since in terms of electricity consumption per capita it lags far behind the other states. Bihar’s power situation shows some progress, but the gap between rural and urban areas remains notable. The attempt here is to use the NTL mapping for Bihar for further clarity.

Fig.:4 NTL status in Bihar from 2012 to 2021

In **2012**, most of Bihar appears dark (black and grey zones), meaning NTL radiance was below 25 nW/cm²/sr. Only a few urban centres—Patna, Gaya, Bhagalpur, Muzaffarpur, and Darbhanga—show notable brightness, indicating concentrated development and electrification. The northern and central rural belts had minimal illumination, reflecting limited access to electricity and low night-time activity. By **2021**, the map shows a dramatic increase in illuminated areas across the state. The yellow and red zones (radiance above 25 nW/cm²/sr)

have spread outward from cities into semi-urban and rural regions. Patna and nearby districts display intense brightness, indicating rapid urban growth, infrastructure expansion, and economic activity. Even previously dark districts like Gaya, Muzaffarpur, and Bhagalpur now show extended light coverage, implying better power access and rural electrification.

Bihar has achieved Widespread Electrification with Urban Growth Corridors – The Patna–Gaya–Bhagalpur belt shows significant urban clustering, reflecting rising industrial and service sector activity. This reflects Shrinking Rural–Urban Divide – Increased illumination in peripheral areas indicating narrowing disparities between urban and rural electricity access. It is worth noting that as an Economic Development Indicator – Higher night-time radiance is correlated with improved living standards, industrialization, and commercial expansion. Although the state has managed to narrow the disparity between urban and rural areas but rural areas in themselves have experienced little change. As a result, the disparity widened again to 685.63 hours (refer table no:2) in 2021-22. This growing gap highlights that rural consumers still face much longer power cuts compared to their urban counterparts. Overall, while Bihar’s power supply reliability is improving, but the benefits are not evenly shared — rural areas continue to lag behind in access to consistent electricity.

According to the news reported in Jul 31, 2024, 12:09:00 PM IST in The Economic Times India could face serious evening power shortages by 2027 — possibly between 20 and 40 gigawatts — even if all the thermal and hydroelectric plants currently being built start running on time, according to the India Energy and Climate Centre (IECC).

For the overall achievement of a healthy economy it is important that every Indian state gets continuous supply of electricity. At the same time India needs to prepare for the surge in demand as more and more parts of India will get urbanized with increases tick in urbanization. To ensure a uniform spread of access and availability the supply of continuous supply of electricity must not be ignored. Schemes like Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gram Jyoti Yojana (DDUGJY) and Saubhagya (Pradhan Mantri Sahaj Bijli Har Ghar Yojana) will help further this endeavour.

Bibliography

Bhandari, Laveesh & Roychowdhury, Koel. (2011). Night Lights and Economic Activity in India: A study using DMSP-OLS night time images. Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Advanced Network. 32. 218. 10.7125/APAN.32.24.

Henderson, J. V., Storeygard, A., & Weil, D. N. (2011). A Bright Idea for Measuring Economic Growth. The American economic review, 101(3), 194–199. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.101.3.194>

National Remote Sensing Centre ISRO, Dept. of Space, Govt. of India Hyderabad – 500 037 (2012 – 2021). A Report on Decadal Change of Night Time Light (NTL) over India from Space.

Disha Agarwal, Arushi Relan, Rudhi Pradhan, Sanyogita Satpute, Karthik Ganesan, and Shalu Agrawal (March 2025). A Report on How can India Meet its Rising Power Demand? Pathways to 2030. The Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW).

Webliography:

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/energy/power/india-may-face-potential-evening-power-shortages-by-2027-warns-iecc/articleshow/112158261.cms?from=mdr>

<https://iecc.gsp.berkeley.edu/impact-areas/power/2/>

<https://iced.niti.gov.in/economy-and-demography/demography>

<https://vedas.sac.gov.in/energymap/view/powergis.jsp>